

MUSEUM RETAILING AND VISITOR SHOPPING EXPERIENCE

Ibroximova Aziza Abbasovna

Toshkent Xalqaro Vestminster universiteti tayanch doktoranti, O‘zbekiston tarixi davlat muzeyi xodimi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20264854>

Abstract. *This article examines museums as multifunctional spaces where shopping is an important part of the visitor experience. It highlights that museum shops influence visitor satisfaction alongside education and exhibition functions. Research shows that factors such as product value, service quality, and the shopping environment strongly affect visitor satisfaction. However, museum shopping remains under-researched compared to general tourism shopping. The literature emphasizes that improving museum retail services can enhance both visitor experience and museum sustainability.*

Keywords: *museum tourism, visitor satisfaction, shopping experience, museum retail, cultural heritage.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada muzeylar tashrif buyuruvchilar uchun xarid qilish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadigan ko'p funksiyali madaniy hudud sifatida tahlil etiladi. Ekspozitsiya va ta'lim -tarbiyaviy vazifalari bilan bir qatorda muzey suvenir do'konlarining tashrif buyuruvchilar mamnuniyatiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatishi ham alohida qayd etiladi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, mahsulot sifati va narxi, xizmat darajasi hamda xarid muhiti tashrif buyuruvchilarning umumiy qoniqish darajasini belgilovchi asosiy omillar hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, muzey savdosi umumiy turizm savdosiga qaraganda ilmiy jihatdan hali yetarli darajada o'rganilmagan soha bo'lib qolmoqda. Adabiyotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, muzeyda suvenir savdo xizmatlarini takomillashtirish nafaqat tashrif buyuruvchilar tajribasini boyitadi, balki muzeylarning uzoq muddatli barqarorligini ta'minlashga ham xizmat qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *muзей turizmi, tashrif buyuruvchilar mamnuniyati, xarid tajribasi, muzey savdosi, madaniy meros.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются музеи как многофункциональные пространства, где шопинг занимает важное место в опыте посетителей. Подчёркивается, что музейные магазины наряду с образовательными и выставочными функциями всё активнее влияют на удовлетворённость посетителей. Исследования показывают, что такие факторы, как ценность продукта, качество обслуживания и торговая среда, существенно сказываются на уровне удовлетворённости. Вместе с тем музейный шопинг остаётся недостаточно изученным по сравнению с туристическим шопингом в целом. В литературе подчёркивается, что совершенствование розничных услуг в музеях способно улучшить как качество обслуживания посетителей, так и устойчивость самих музеев.*

Ключевые слова: *музейный туризм, удовлетворённость посетителей, опыт шопинга, музейная торговля, культурное наследие.*

Museum tourism is an important platform for showcasing the unique cultures and histories of cities¹. Visitors' shopping experiences are shaped by the level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction they derive from the products and services they purchase². Museums have gradually evolved from traditional “cabinets of curiosities,” focused primarily on preserving collections, into cultural consumption spaces that contribute to economic development and tourism infrastructure³. Contemporary discussions increasingly portray museums as “cultural shops”⁴, where visitors engage with, enjoy, and consume a wide range of educational, cultural, and commercial products. Although extensive research has examined shopping experiences and visitor satisfaction in tourism⁵, the role of shopping within museum tourism remains relatively underexplored.

With the development of urban destinations, the tourism function of museums has become increasingly prominent. In terms of museum functions, most scholars agree that museums have developed into multi-functional institutions integrating education, leisure, entertainment, and social significance rather than merely providing the collection, protection, and exhibition of cultural and spiritual heritage⁶. Kotler explained that, in addition to providing educational and display functions, museums now present a trend of providing participatory, social, and recreational experiences⁷.

Researchers are increasingly exploring the motivations of museum visitors as well as their needs, experiences and satisfaction, as well as their behavioral characteristics. For example, McLean found that most people's motivation in visiting a museum was to gain more cultural knowledge to enrich their life experiences⁸. The current research on museum tourism development focuses on the design and creation of resources and products as well as the current status and future trends in museum tourism. For example, Chen, Lee, Lin, and Wang used the decision-making trial and evaluation laboratory method to explore the critical factors influencing visitors to purchase museum cultural products⁹. Overall, despite the growing body of research on museum tourism, limited attention has been given to visitors' shopping experiences and levels of satisfaction within museums.

Shopping is one of the important tourist activities and is acknowledged as a primary travel

¹ Chen, Q.; Li, Q.; Zhang, S.L. A review of museum tourism research at home and abroad. *Hum. Geogr.* 2012, 27, 24–30.

² C. Tosun, S.P. Temizkan, D.J. Timothy, A. Fyall. Tourist shopping experiences and satisfaction. *Int. J. Tour. Res.* 2007, 9, 87–102.

³ E. Booth, R. Powell. Museums: From cabinets of curiosity to cultural shopping experiences. In *Tourism and Culture in the Age of Innovation*; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2016; pp. 131–143.

⁴ J. Larkin. All Museums Will Become Department Stores: The Development and Implications of Retailing at Museums and Heritage Sites. *Archaeol. Int.* 2016, 19, 109–121.

⁵ V.C. Heung, E. Cheng. Assessing tourists' satisfaction with shopping in the Hong Kong special administrative region of China. *J. Travel Res.* 2000, 38, 396–404.

⁶ H.M. Lee, S.L.J. Smith. A visitor experience scale: Historic sites and museums. *J. China Tour. Res.* 2015, 11, 255–277.

⁷ N. Kotler. New ways of experiencing culture: The role of museums and marketing implications. *Mus. Manag. Curatorship* 2004, 19, 417–425.

⁸ F. McLean. Understanding the Public: A Challenge to Museums. In *Proceedings of the 23rd EMAC Conference: Marketing, its Dynamics and Challenges*, Bloemer, Lemmink, and Kasper, Maastricht, The Netherlands, 17–20 May 1994; Volume 2, pp. 1399–1401.

⁹ Y.H. Chen, C. Lee, C.T. Lin, S.W. Wang. Using the DEMATEL Method to Explore the Critical Factors That Influence Visitors to Purchase Museum Cultural Products. *J. Test. Eval.* 2018, 46, 2045–2055.

motive¹⁰. Given its importance, more researchers are paying attention to the shopping experience within tourism. However, museum shopping experiences have received scant attention. Museums are an integral component of cultural heritage and are important heritage attractions, especially within major cities¹¹. If visiting museums is regarded as a form of tourism, the shopping experiences of museum visitors may bear some similarities to other tourism shopping experiences¹².

While the growing development of shop revenues reflects the professionalization of selling practices, it is also indicative of the importance of the shop to visitor satisfaction. Recent research across six museum and heritage sites in England, showed that 80% of visitors had some interaction with the shop¹³. Museum retail growth is reshaping how museums are experienced, with gift shops influencing visitor flow and becoming attractions in their own right, affecting how culture is presented overall¹⁴. The result is that neither academics nor practitioners have developed the tools or conceptual approaches to analyse the museum shop effectively, and therefore do not clearly understand how commerce within a cultural context may influence the visit. Consequently, the shop (alongside the café) is among the least scrutinised and therefore most poorly understood aspects of the contemporary museum experience.

The above-mentioned definition of shopping tourism developed by Tosun et al.¹⁵ has been confirmed by many scholars who have found that satisfaction with a series of shopping attributes such as products, services, and shopping environment leads to overall satisfaction with shopping experiences. For example, Wong and Wan defined tourist shopping satisfaction as a four-dimensional construct, including service product and environment, merchandise value, staff service quality, and service differentiation. They pointed out that positive assessments of these dimensions generate pleasant shopping experiences for visitors¹⁶. Heung and Cheng divided shopping attributes into four dimensions: staff service quality, product value, product reliability, and tangible quality. They found that staff service quality had the greatest effect on visitor satisfaction when shopping in Hong Kong, followed by product value and product reliability¹⁷. The role of museum retail spaces has been redefined, becoming a more important element of museum visits¹⁸. Kent argued that museum shops play an important role in creating interactivity and recreational experiences that supplement the museum’s educational priorities¹⁹.

¹⁰ I.A. Wong, Y.K.P. Wan. A systematic approach to scale development in tourist shopping satisfaction: Linking destination attributes and shopping experience. *J. Travel Res.* 2013, 52, 29–41.

¹¹ M. Jansen-Verbeke, J. Van Rekom. Scanning museum visitors: Urban tourism marketing. *Ann. Tour. Res.* 1996, 23, 364–375.

¹² C.W. Sheng, M.C. Chen. A study of experience expectations of museum visitors. *Tour. Manag.* 2012, 33, 53–60.

¹³ J. Larkin. *Trading on the Past: An examination of the cultural and economic roles of shops at museums and heritage sites in England*. Unpublished thesis (PhD), University College London, 2016.

¹⁴ J. Larkin. All Museums Will Become Department Stores’: The Development and Implications of Retailing at Museums and Heritage Sites. *Archaeology International*, 2016. No. 19: pp. 109–121 // <http://dx.doi.org/10.5334/ai.1917>

¹⁵ C. Tosun, S.P. Temizkan, D.J. Timothy, A. Fyall. Tourist shopping experiences and satisfaction. *Int. J. Tour. Res.* 2007, 9, 87–102.

¹⁶ I.A. Wong, Y.K.P. Wan. A systematic approach to scale development in tourist shopping satisfaction: Linking destination attributes and shopping experience. *J. Travel Res.* 2013, 52, 29–41.

¹⁷ V.C. Heung, E. Cheng. Assessing tourists’ satisfaction with shopping in the Hong Kong special administrative region of China. *J. Travel Res.* 2000, 38, 396–404.

¹⁸ E. Booth, R. Powell. *Museums: From cabinets of curiosity to cultural shopping experiences*. In *Tourism and Culture in the Age of Innovation*; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2016; pp. 131–143.

¹⁹ T. Kent. The role of the museum shop in extending the visitor experience. *Int. J. Nonprofit Volunt. Sect. Mark.* 2010, 15, 67–77.

According to Shao et.al. visitors' shopping experiences in National Gallery (NG) are related to many factors. Among them, the factors that worsen shopping experiences mainly include the cost-value of the paid products and services, staff service attitudes, and the environmental facilities of the museum²⁰. Tony Kent highlights that museum shops are an important part of the visitor experience. Unlike the formal museum environment, shops provide a relaxed and interactive space where visitors can freely touch, explore, and purchase items. They connect visitors back to everyday life while still maintaining a link to the museum's cultural atmosphere. Museum shops also support informal learning through educational products and help visitors reflect on and personalize their museum experience²¹.

The researchs show that the environmental facilities in the museum also have a significant impact on the shopping experiences of visitors. This is reflected in the cleanliness of facilities, a quiet atmosphere of the museum, and an absence of crowding. Accordingly, museums should ensure the comfort and cleanliness of facilities at all times. During peak periods, museums need to take some specific measures, such as limiting the number of visitors every day and offering different priced tickets, to ensure that visitors get an optimum experience.

In terms of the paid products and services, visitors are very concerned about the price–value–performance ratios of the products and services they purchase, which directly affects their shopping experiences. Furthermore, the research found that when visitors enjoyed paid products and services, they expected to get enhanced experiences related to their purchases. The revenue from paid products and services accounts for a sizeable part of the museum's income; similarly, products and services valued by tourists can expand the viability and influence of the museum. Therefore, museums should pay attention to and constantly optimize the design of paid-for products and services to enhance visitor experiences and satisfaction.

References

1. Chen, Q.; Li, Q.; Zhang, S.L. A review of museum tourism research at home and abroad. *Hum. Geogr.* 2012, 27, 24–30.
2. C. Tosun, S.P.Temizkan, D.J. Timothy, A. Fyall. Tourist shopping experiences and satisfaction. *Int. J. Tour. Res.* 2007, 9, 87–102.
3. E. Booth, R. Powell. Museums: From cabinets of curiosity to cultural shopping experiences. In *Tourism and Culture in the Age of Innovation*; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2016; pp. 131–143.
4. J. Larkin. All Museums Will Become Department Stores: The Development and Implications of Retailing at Museums and Heritage Sites. *Archaeol. Int.* 2016, 19, 109–121.
5. V.C. Heung, E. Cheng. Assessing tourists' satisfaction with shopping in the Hong Kong special administrative region of China. *J. Travel Res.* 2000, 38, 396–404.
6. H.M. Lee, S.L.J. Smith. A visitor experience scale: Historic sites and museums. *J. China Tour. Res.* 2015, 11, 255–277.
7. N. Kotler. New ways of experiencing culture: The role of museums and marketing implications. *Mus. Manag. Curatorship* 2004, 19, 417–425.

²⁰ J. Shao, Q. Ying, S.Shu, A.M. Morrison, E. Booth. Museum Tourism 2.0: Experiences and Satisfaction with Shopping at the National Gallery in London. *Sustainability* 2019, 11, 7108. // <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11247108>

²¹ T. Kent. The role of the museum shop in extending the visitor experience. *Int. J. Nonprofit Volunt. Sect. Mark.* 2010, 15, 67–77.

8. F. McLean. Understanding the Public: A Challenge to Museums. In Proceedings of the 23rd EMAC Conference: Marketing, its Dynamics and Challenges, Bloemer, Lemmink, and Kasper, Maastricht, The Netherlands, 17–20 May 1994; Volume 2, pp. 1399–1401.
9. Y.H. Chen, C. Lee, C.T. Lin, S.W. Wang. Using the DEMATEL Method to Explore the Critical Factors That Influence Visitors to Purchase Museum Cultural Products. *J. Test. Eval.* 2018, 46, 2045–2055.
10. I.A. Wong, Y.K.P. Wan. A systematic approach to scale development in tourist shopping satisfaction: Linking destination attributes and shopping experience. *J. Travel Res.* 2013, 52, 29–41.
11. M. Jansen-Verbeke, J. Van Rekom. Scanning museum visitors: Urban tourism marketing. *Ann. Tour. Res.* 1996, 23, 364–375.
12. C.W. Sheng, M.C. Chen. A study of experience expectations of museum visitors. *Tour. Manag.* 2012, 33, 53–60.
13. J. Larkin. Trading on the Past: An examination of the cultural and economic roles of shops at museums and heritage sites in England. Unpublished thesis (PhD), University College London, 2016.
14. T. Kent. The role of the museum shop in extending the visitor experience. *Int. J. Nonprofit Volunt. Sect. Mark.* 2010, 15, 67–77.
15. J. Shao, Q. Ying, S. Shu, A.M. Morrison, E. Booth. Museum Tourism 2.0: Experiences and Satisfaction with Shopping at the National Gallery in London. *Sustainability* 2019, 11, 7108. // <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11247108>
16. J. Larkin. Trading on the Past: An examination of the cultural and economic roles of shops at museums and heritage sites in England. Unpublished thesis (PhD), University College London, 2016.
17. J. Larkin. All Museums Will Become Department Stores’: The Development and Implications of Retailing at Museums and Heritage Sites. *Archaeology International* , 2016. No. 19: pp. 109–121 // <http://dx.doi.org/10.5334/ai.1917>